

WP4 - Bringing interactions between actors to a new level: living labs and virtual space

Deliverable 4.1: Needs and wants of DigitAF Living Labs for digital tools for agroforestry

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Summary

The DigitAF project (2022-2026) works on the development of digital tools for three main actor groups: policy actors, practitioners and beneficiaries of AF products and services. In the first year of DigitAF (2022-2023), six Living Labs (LL) were set up to better understand the needs of actor groups and to later test and evaluate digital tools. The Living Labs, situated in Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands and United Kingdom, were established in different European regions, with different pedoclimatic conditions, types of farming, and types of agroforestry systems (AFS). Although the composition of each LL differs, they all have a balanced composition and ratio of participants.

A survey was set up to understand about the use, the needs and wants of the various stakeholders on digital tools. Questions from all DigitAF work packages (WPs) were assembled and merged aiming to discover the perceptions of stakeholders involved in agroforestry. The survey covered a range of issues regarding agroforestry practices in Europe: policy, biodiversity, agronomy, finance, use and needs of digital tools. An GDPR compliant Google Forms was used to set up an online survey in English that was later translated into Czech, Dutch, Finnish, German and Italian languages and contexts.

The number of respondents per LL ranged between 3 in Finland to 20 in Czechia. Each LL obtained inputs from all three major actor groups, e.g., policymakers, practitioners, and those involved in the value chain. The needs and wants surrounding digital tools for agroforestry were identified.

The outcomes demonstrate a high demand for tools for the design and management of agroforestry systems, as well as decision support tools on financial aspects and tree and crop performance. The prediction and monitoring of ecosystem services (with emphasis on carbon and biodiversity) were also identified as important topics for tool development. Furthermore, all LL made suggestions to improve user-friendliness of new tools.

Despite the similarities, there were also regional differences, which allow LL for co-development of research ideas and tailor-made solutions. The next steps include a match-making exercise between identified needs and available tools and data, assessing appropriateness of selected tools in collaboration with LL participants, followed by testing and further developing these tools in an iterative process.

1 Introduction

1.1 DigitAF project

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools to answer their needs, in particular digital tools. Three actors' groups are targeted by DigitAF:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AF and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading carbon and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

When understanding the needs of these three actor groups with regard to agroforestry altogether, the consortium works towards developing tailor-made digital tools that address these needs. The activities of the project are divided into six work packages. Table 1 gives an overview of their content.

Table 1. *DigitAF Work Packages (WPs)*

Work Package titles	Main focus
WP1: <i>Strengthening agroforestry and carbon farming policies: tools for policy-makers</i>	<i>The development of digital tools for policymakers, by among other things, reviewing current policy, making recommendations for standardisation to policymakers, including agroforestry to existing policy frameworks and tools.</i>
WP2: <i>Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors</i>	<i>The development of hands-on tools for practitioners and farm advisors, such as tools to improve farm-technical & economic, labor and administrative aspects and tools to assess, predict and optimise tree and crop performance in AFS.</i>
WP3: <i>Accounting agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries in agroforestry value chains</i>	<i>The development of digital tools for other beneficiaries in the AF value chain, by identifying and mapping key actors and implementing biodiversity and carbon calculator tools as well as soil health tools</i>
WP4: <i>Bringing interactions between actors to a new level: LL and a common agroforestry toolbox</i>	<i>Connecting all WPs to 6 Living Labs with European agroforestry actors. Evaluates and selects existing open-access data sources and tools and provides a virtual space to make data and tools available to stakeholders.</i>

WP5 - Getting actors to act:
dissemination, exploitation and communication

Effective dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy, ensure wide-scale uptake of project results and monitors the projection and management of knowledge created in the project.

Six *Living Labs* (LL) were formed with members consisting of all actor groups to understand the needs of each actor groups, and to test and evaluate digital tools. A first step was to analyse the needs and wants of the members of these Living Labs and summarize the outcomes in this report.

1.2 About this report

This report describes the six LLs (Chapter 2) and outlines their first activities, namely a country specific kick-off meeting as well as a unified survey aimed at collecting the needs of the actor groups (Chapter 3). A more elaborate description of the methods used can be found in paragraph 3.1. The results of the survey are displayed per Living Lab in paragraph 3.2. Conclusions and outlook are presented in Chapter 4.

2 Description of Living Labs

2.1 Six Living Labs

Six Living Labs were created (or expanded) to ensure that end-users' needs and feedback are proactively considered throughout the project development. The LL situated in Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, United Kingdom and The Netherlands, were established in different European regions, with different pedoclimatic conditions, types of farming, and types of agroforestry systems (AFS). They serve as fora for end-users and developers of tools to work together. LL are local networks of selected actors. They consist of an integrated group of practitioners, policymakers, and other beneficiaries. The Living Lab approach encourages the use of different methods. We used surveys and questionnaires, focus groups, and workshops.

Advanced and Seed Living Labs

In the project, two different types of LLs were differentiated: advanced and seed LLs. Three LLs were qualified as advanced LL. Germany, the Netherlands, and Italy use existing networks that already gather representatives of DigitAF's three target groups from the project's onset. Advanced LLs can also advise seed LLs in ways through which other target actors can be involved in the LLs.

Seed LL (in Czechia, Finland, and the UK) started from existing networks or initiatives that gather a given group of stakeholders and expanded the diversity of actors involved in the LL during the project.

General synthesis of the LL

At the end of the first year of the project, the LLs differed in size, but managed to have a balanced composition with practitioners, policy actors and other beneficiaries. All LL had an initial meeting in the period December 2022-March 2023 and most had a second meeting to discuss the outcomes of the questionnaire. (Table 2).

Table 2. *Living Lab members and meetings*

LL	Practitioners	Policy actors	Other beneficiaries		Meetings
			Value chain	Other stakeholders	
CZ	27 (22 farmers, 5 advisors)	7	2	5 NGO	December 2022 May 2023
FI	7 (6 farmers, 1 advisor)	2	1	6 (4 teachers 2 researchers)	January 2023
DE	4	3	2	2 (1 env. NGO, 1 education)	Individual meetings with LL members
IT	10 (4 farmers, 6 advisors)		2		January 2023 May 2023
NL	8 (6 farmers, 2 advisors)	6	2		December 2022 May 2023
UK	4	3	2		March 2023 April 2023

2.2 Living Lab The Netherlands (Advanced)

2.2.1 AGROFORESTRY IN THE NETHERLANDS

Apart from small areas of cultural historic agroforestry landscapes, agroforestry is a particularly recent movement in The Netherlands. The earliest adopters of agroforestry in The Netherlands are livestock farmers. Since 2008 a small group of poultry farmers started to experiment with planting trees in their free-range areas. Despite the considerable interest in this practice in the poultry sector, agroforestry on poultry farms is slowed down by the appearance of bird flu and the prohibition to keep chickens outside. Parallel to poultry farmers, dairy farmers started to get interested in planting trees and shrubs for biomass, biodiversity, animal welfare and fodder. Recently, the practice of fodder trees was adopted by a larger group of dairy farmers. Also, silvopastoral systems with standard fruit trees, walnut trees and hazelnut shrubs increased in popularity over the years. Dairy farmers now form the dominant group of agroforestry practitioners. Only in recent years, a small group of arable farmers started to show interest in agroforestry and a handful started alley cropping systems. It can be stated that the number of farmers involved in agroforestry is in the hundreds. These farmers either recently started their agroforestry system or are in an advanced stage of their plans to realize agroforestry. The vast majority of this group (estimated over 95%) planted trees in the last 5 years. Most of the agroforestry farmers have relatively dry sandy soils, although recently also farmers with clay soil types started adopting agroforestry.

2.2.2 FORMATION OF LIVING LAB THE NETHERLANDS

Agroforestry in The Netherlands is characterized as a typical bottom-up movement. Starting in 2008, farmers interested in agroforestry grouped together to take the realization of agroforestry on their farms a step further. These so-called 'provincial study groups' started in the provinces of Noord-Brabant and Gelderland, followed by initiatives in other provinces. During the period 2018-2021, several reports have been prepared on behalf of the Ministry of Agriculture on how agroforestry could be scaled up in The Netherlands. It was suggested that one of the ways forward was to connect the different local groups in an overarching national network. The goal of this network is to forge a strong connection between practitioners (farmers and advisors), knowledge institutions and policymakers. At the end of 2021, Agroforestry Netwerk Nederland (ANN) was founded. Since then, the ANN has acted as an organization that is committed to agroforestry practice, by identifying and removing obstacles and making information available.

Agroforestry in The Netherlands, is a recent movement and agroforestry systems are not in production yet. Therefore, the value chain for agroforestry products is non-existent. However, some food chain actors are interested in the development of agroforestry products and value chains. Since both these actors as well as the ANN are acting on a national level, it was decided the Living Lab The Netherlands also needed to operate on a national level. As a result of geographically including the entire country in the LL, the number of potential participating farmers was large. Potentially highly motivated farmers were approached individually. Within the ANN a separate appeal was made to policymakers and other beneficiaries to sign up for the LL.

2.2.3 COMPOSITION OF LIVING LAB THE NETHERLANDS

The initial LL was formed in December of 2022 when the first meeting took place. A second meeting took place in the following year in May (Figure 1).

Figure 1. *The second meeting of the Living Lab Netherlands, May 2023.*

The LL consists of 16 individuals. Practitioners are represented by six farmers from different agricultural sectors and different levels of experience with agroforestry. Also, a coordinator of local agroforestry farmers networks is included, as well as an advisor for small-scale agroforestry systems. Policy representatives include policymakers on both national and provincial levels. The group of ‘other beneficiaries’ consists of a value chain developer and an agroforestry tree nursery grower. The group of other beneficiaries is relatively small. When needed, other participants from this category will be approached when it becomes more concrete which tools will be developed. In general, the formation of the LL is considered flexible. While there is a focus on the long-term commitment of the different partners, it is expected the composition of the group will change over the years to match DigitAF project’s goals with the interests of the participants.

2.3 Living Lab Germany (Advanced)

2.3.1 AGROFORESTRY PRACTICES IN GERMANY

Germany has a unique heritage of traditional agroforestry systems, with its meadow orchards, windbreaks, the “Knicks” in Schleswig-Holstein in the North to the Hag-landscapes in Bavaria in the South. These small-scale and complex structures have been displaced by larger structured land use models in the course of technological progress. From this perspective, modern agroforestry systems could offer an approach (and partial substitute) to combine agricultural use with benefits for landscape, environment and increase resilience towards the climate crisis.

Of the 142 agroforestry sites presented on the agroforestry map of Germany, 71 are categorized as silvopastoral system, so the majority of the entries are thus agroforestry systems in which woody plants are planted on grassland or are combined with livestock farming. 49 of the agroforestry areas are silvoarable systems, 22 others are agrosilvopastoral systems (DeFAF 2023).

2.3.2 AGROFORESTRY SUPPORT IN GERMANY

In summer 2021, the German Bundestag passed a legislative package to implement the reform of the CAP. Since then, agroforestry systems have been eligible for support. As a result, agroforestry was included in the funding strategy of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture for arable land, permanent grassland, and in permanent crops, whereby agroforestry must serve for raw material extraction and/or food production. In the CAP Strategic Plan for Germany 2022, agroforestry is characterized as woody plants with the primary objective to produce raw material or food in accordance with a

utilisation concept (verified by the federal states or by an institution recognised by them). Moreover, at least two woody strips covering less than 40% of the agricultural area or scattered over the area in a number of at least 50 and no more than 200 such woody plants per hectare. CAP Conditionality Ordinance regulates the implementation with binding environmental requirements and requirements for the receipt of CAP payments. The voluntary EcoScheme, a 1st pillar measure, started in 2023. The EcoScheme named "Maintenance of agroforestry management on arable land and permanent grassland" allows to apply for 60 €/ha*yr only for the wooded area share in the future. An exclusion list for certain woody plants applies, as well as regulations on minimum and maximum distances in relation to the location of the agroforestry woody plants (Hübner 2022 a, b). However, the application rate for the EcoScheme falls very far short of the expectations of 25,000 ha of woody plant area in 2023. Only 51 ha by 67 farms applied for funding in 2023 (Lehmann 2023); it remains more than questionable how the target of 200,000 ha in the current funding period will be achieved. In the future, the establishment and maintenance of agroforestry systems are also to be promoted within the framework of federal state support via European agricultural fund for rural development (EAFRD), i.e. funds from the so-called 2nd pillar. The federal states are taking different approaches. In Brandenburg, where the DigiAF LL is located, funding is envisaged through investment support. Some federal states will not offer any support for agroforestry. Although the European Commission provides support of up to 100% of costs in the CAP Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, it is becoming apparent that support via EAFRD-Investment will comprise 40% of the eligible costs and that a minimum investment of 20,000 € must be achieved. In order for the federal states to also be able to call on federal funds, it is currently desirable to anchor agroforestry in the national "Improvement of Agricultural Structure and Coastal Protection" (GAK) framework. This Joint Task is the most important national funding instrument for supporting agriculture and forestry, developing rural areas, and improving coastal and flood protection.

2.3.3 FORMATION OF LIVING LAB GERMANY

A large part of the federal state Brandenburg, where the DigiAF LL is located, is used for agriculture and is available as potential land for the cultivation of agroforestry systems (Figure 2).

In 2021, the agriculturally used area in the state of Brandenburg covered 1.3 million ha. Arable land represented the foremost land use with about 1 million ha, followed by permanent grassland with 0.3 million ha.

Figure 2. *Map of Germany divided by federal state, type and extent of agroforestry areas. The colours brown, yellow and green represent the type of agroforestry system. The size of the pie chart stands for the relative area per federal state. The LL Germany is highlighted in light blue (Source: DeFAF 2023).*

As the Brandenburg region has many areas with unfavourable farming conditions, e.g., with regard to soil type, water retention capacity, susceptibility to erosion, conventional arable farming cannot guarantee sufficient protection of the resources soil, water, and biodiversity. These fragile resources can be enhanced by the establishment of agroforestry systems. At the same time, the LL Brandenburg is one of the regions in Germany most affected by the climate crisis, so agroforestry systems can be expected to have a particularly positive effect. In the Brandenburg region, financial support for the establishment of agroforestry systems is planned for 2023.

The LL Germany comprises a large number of interesting personalities from the agroforestry scene in Brandenburg, some of whom have many years of experience in agroforestry. One example is the farm of Thomas Domin (Figure 3).

Figure 3. *Modern agroforestry system with poplar, black locust and various deciduous tree species, interspersed with cropland and forage land, so called alley cropping system.*

Thomas Domin planted the first agroforestry system within the project AUFWERTEN in 2015 with seven alley cropping strips on agricultural land (about 5 ha), mainly with poplar for energy production. In 2016, two strips (1 ha) of permanent grassland completed the system. In 2020, the AF was expanded by three additional woody strips (about 2 ha) on arable land with trees and shrubs (Böhm & Hübner 2020). An orchard system as a compensation measure as well as rows of fruit trees along former roads have recently been added. 8.9 ha, that is about 10% of the farmland, are stocked with various trees and bushes.

The German Agroforestry Association (www.defaf.de) maintains intensive and regular contact with the stakeholders and organises various events. These range from farm days, presentations, and participation in trade fairs to cultural events such as celebrating a cinema evening. In the further course of the project, the main focus will be on the further development and testing of digital tools in the field of agroforestry. There is a very high level of interest in this. Now, the LL Germany group is being completed to include more farms and representatives from politics and administration, especially in order to address a less experienced group of participants. The group might fluctuate and is characterised by different intensities of participation, depending on interest and time availability.

2.4 Living Lab Italy – Tuscany (Advanced)

2.4.1 AGROFORESTRY IN ITALY

Italy has the fourth largest area of agroforestry in Europe of about 1.4 million ha and the fourth largest area for livestock agroforestry systems. Traditionally, in the Tuscany region, agroforestry practices were mainly represented by (i) the cultivation of trees outside forest as field hedgerows delivering multifunctional products essential for smallholders and subsistence farmers, (ii) silvopastoralism including the extensive and semi-extensive management for beef cattle, dairy sheep and goats and (iii) by traditional agroforestry systems based on the integration of crops and/or animals in low-density olive tree orchards. Due to the Green Revolution transformation, agroforestry practices became obsolete because multifunctional agriculture was substituted by more specialized systems. Recently,

the European Commission's choice to include agroforestry as a practice for carbon farming and other EcoSchemes related with adaptation and mitigation of climate change, prevention of land degradation and protection of biodiversity makes agroforestry subsidies more appealing for farmers and landowners compared to the past CAP.

2.4.2 FORMATION OF THE LIVING LAB

The advanced Italian LL was developed starting from a pre-existing network formed during the EIP-AGRI OG NEWTON (Sub-measure 16.2, RDP 2014-2020 of the Tuscany Region). In January 2023, during the final event of NEWTON after the presentation of the project results, the DIGITAF project and the LL activities were presented to farmers, advisors, and policymakers. Subsequently, additional actors of the beef value chain were personally invited to extend the previously existing NEWTON network. As mentioned, the Italian LL is focused on the beef value chain which is one of the most valuable agricultural value chains of Tuscany.

2.4.3 DESCRIPTION OF THE LIVING LAB

The Italian LL covers the entire area of the Tuscany Region which comprehend about one million ha of arable land and one million ha of forest land. The LL is a balanced team composed by four farmers (three livestock and one olive farmer), six advisors (one veterinary, one environmental and three agronomist), a certification company and a start-up company for the market of sustainable beef. Within the farmers and advisors' groups there are stakeholders that already practice or have a good knowledge about agroforestry systems but there are also stakeholders willing and interested in knowing more about agroforestry practices to implement them in their farms or to support farmers. During the first meetings of the LL, policymaker stakeholders were not involved in LL activities, but they will be included in the LL later on.

2.5 Living Lab United Kingdom (Seed)

The United Kingdom Living Lab is a 'seed' LL, which has been created for the project based on a group of interested stakeholders, involving practitioners, policymakers and other actors in the value chain.

2.5.1 AGROFORESTRY PRACTICE IN THE UK

Traditional agroforestry systems in the UK include shelterwoods (cattle and sheep taking shelter in mature woodlands), pannage (pigs herded into woodlands/orchards to eat fallen tree fruits), grazing livestock in open parkland, and farm and orchard shelterbelts. There is also a long history of hedgerow management. An example of modern agroforestry in the UK is the establishment of alley cropping systems by Bryant and May (Forestry) Ltd in the 1970s. They established a silvoarable system cultivating poplars with cereals in between the tree rows, cropping these alleys with cereal for 7-8 years. Then the system transitioned into a silvopastoral system, where cropping in between rows was discontinued to be replaced by grazing livestock (Hislop and Claridge, 2000).

In 1984, research interest in agroforestry started to pick up among agricultural research centres, with the first simulation models developed during the period 1985-1986. In 1987, a multi-site national silvopastoral experiment was started, the National Network Experiment, including sites in Northern Ireland, Scotland, England and Wales. A national silvoarable network of three sites was established in 1992. The first agroforestry newsletter was published in 1990, called 'Agroforestry Forum'. In 1987, the 'Agroforestry Research: UK Discussion Forum' was created in parallel to the National Network Experiment, which then changed its name to the 'UK Agroforestry Research Forum' in 1991, the 'UK Agroforestry Forum' in 1998, and the 'Farm Woodland Forum' in 2003.

In recent years, agroforestry is being increasingly practised by entrepreneurial and innovative farmers, supported by the involvement of organisations such as the Farm Woodland Forum, the Woodland Trust, and the Soil Association. A UK Agroforestry Handbook was published in 2019 (Raskin and Osborn 2019). From the early 1990s, several UK research institutions have been actively taking part in international agroforestry research projects in collaboration with other countries thanks to EU funding. These include: ALWAYS, based on the National Network Experiment (1994), SAFE (2001-2005), AGFORWARD (2014-2017), and AGROMIX (2020-2024).

2.5.2 FORMATION OF THE UK DIGITAF LIVING LAB

Using established contacts, a group of potentially interested stakeholders covering practitioners, policymakers, and those in the value chain was identified focused on the East Midlands and Eastern part of England. Staff from Cranfield University contacted the potential stakeholders individually and once they agreed to take part, a first meeting of the UK DIGITAF Living Lab was convened. It was decided that it would be useful to refer to the group as the UK DIGITAF Living Lab, as other agroforestry living labs have been or are being developed as part of different project with different geographical spreads. Composition of the UK Living Lab

The LL currently consists of ten individuals. Policy representatives include two members of the UK Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) and one member from the UK Forestry Commission. Practitioners are represented by four farmers with different agroforestry systems in place (silvoarable, silvopastoral, research focus, wildlife focus, conservation focus). The stakeholders from the value chain include one member from the Farm Carbon Toolkit and one member of the Woodland Trust. While there is a focus on long-term commitment of the different partners, it is expected that the composition of the group might change over the years to match DigitAF project's goals with interests of the participants.

The initial LL was formed in March 2023, with the first meeting taking place online on 7 March 2023. The needs and expectations of the industry were discussed during this initial meeting. A second meeting was held with one of the farmers to establish further collaboration activities on 13 April 2023.

2.6 Living Lab Czechia (Seed)

Living Lab Czechia is a seed Living Lab, which means it is based on a new group of practitioners, policymakers, and other beneficiaries.

2.6.1 AGROFORESTRY PRACTICE IN CZECHIA

Agroforestry (AF) used to be a relatively common land use in the Czech Republic, but was largely eliminated from the landscape due to the agricultural intensification, merging field blocks or abandonment of less productive areas, accelerated mainly during the era of collectivization after World War II. The agricultural intensification has marginalized traditional AF practices to areas with environmental constraints for intensive agriculture, where the only remnants of traditional agroforestry systems can be found. Most of the silvopastoral AF were converted to tree-less pastures or were reforested. On fertile lowland, with predominance of arable farming, AF completely disappeared. Currently, traditional AF systems can be found on less than 1% of agricultural land in the Czech Republic, all of them classified as silvopastoral AF (wood pastures or orchard grazing). Silvoarable AF plots are being established by some progressive farmers, but also research institutions and universities for research and demonstration purposes (Figure 4). Despite their low extent, these areas are of high natural and cultural value, because the vegetation complexity and (species) diversity provides a wide range of ecosystem and cultural services. In the last years we can see the growing interest among farmers, land owners, policymakers, and other stakeholder of reintroduction of AF on

agricultural land in Czechia. This movement has been mainly supported by the Czech Association for Agroforestry (ČSAL), together with the Association of Private Farming (one of the main farmers associations).

Figure 4. *Silvoarable agroforestry plot established by VUKOZ in Pruhonice, Czechia.*

Agroforestry has been included in the Czech CAP Strategic Plan 2023–27 and The Czech Ministry of Agriculture, together with ČSAL and other stakeholders, prepared a new AF measure (one of the Agri-Climate-Environment Measures) to support establishment and maintenance of AF. This has been prepared for the new Czech Rural Development Plan, and established AF parcels will be registered by farmers in the Czech Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS)—as crop type subcategories on arable land or permanent grassland. Two categories are currently supported: (i) silvoarable AF (75–100 forest or fruit trees per ha grown in alley cropping design on arable land; and (ii) silvopastoral AF (75–100 scattered/lined trees per ha on permanent grasslands). More than 50% of the individual trees must be forest species. A list of permitted tree species for AF has been prepared and it is divided into primary tree species, for which subsidies is given, and supplementary tree species and shrubs, which are not subsidized. The measure includes a condition that one tree species must not account for more than 40% of all tree species (i.e., at least three species must be planted) and at least 50% of trees must be forest trees. Financial support is provided for the establishment (4,353 €/ha), and maintenance (754 €/ha*year) during five years after establishment

2.6.2 FORMATION OF LIVING LAB CZECHIA

Czech LL consists of a diverse group of practitioners (farmers and advisors), policymakers (national and local), and other beneficiaries (NGOs and private companies). It was established at a national level and covers the whole country, but a high number of participants are from two regions: Central Bohemia and South Moravia. The LL Czechia is shared with another HORIZON project (REFOREST) to strengthen complementary benefits of both projects. Based on the ČSAL network, highly motivated farmers were approached individually, as well as the well-known policymakers and beneficiaries.

2.6.3 COMPOSITION OF LIVING LAB CZECHIA

The initial LL was formed in December 2022, when the first meeting took place. A second meeting took place in the following year in May (Figure 5).

Figure 5. *The second meeting of the Living Lab Czechia, May 2023.*

The LL now consists of around 40 participants. Practitioners are represented by 22 farmers from different agricultural sectors (crop, animal, mixed production), different size and different levels of experience with agroforestry. Five agroforestry advisors are included in the LL. Altogether, seven policy representatives in the LL include policymakers on both national (Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Environment, Nature Conservation Agency, State Agriculture Intervention Fund and Local Action Groups Centre) and provincial level (Municipality of South Moravia and Central Bohemia). The group of ‘other beneficiaries’ consists of two private companies (Carboneg, BigTerra) and five NGOs (ČSAL, APF, Partnership Fund, Live Water, Live Soil and ZaZemí) all working in the area of ecosystem services valuation. Under negotiation is a cooperation with Czech Association for Regenerative Farming and its particular members (farmers). If needed, other participants from each category will be approached when specific tools will be developed. In general, the formation of the LL Czechia is considered flexible. While there is a focus on long-term commitment of the different partners, it is expected that the composition of the group will change over the years to match DigitAF project’s goals with interests of the participants.

2.7 Living Lab Finland (Seed)

2.7.1 AGROFORESTRY PRACTICE IN FINLAND

Although agroforestry is not very often associated to northern European climatic zones, agroforestry has a long tradition in Finland. The most well-known examples of agroforestry practices in northern Fennoscandia are reindeer husbandry and the collection of non-wood forest products such as berries, mushrooms and wild herbs.

Grazing of forests and wood pastures is another agroforestry practice found in Finland and has been practised since ancient times. Very often grazing followed slash-and-burn cultivation to clear forests and make them temporarily suitable for the cultivation of cereals and vegetables. Slash-and-burn cultivation was practiced until the end of the 19th century when the use of forest for timber production started to provide a higher added value to wood. Forest grazing was still common in Finland in the 1930s but disappeared almost completely in the 1950s with the intensification of agriculture and forestry. In Finland, there were still about 2 million ha of forest and wood pastures in the 1950s. Since then, the area of wood pastures (in Finnish: *hakamaita*) has decreased to about 1,900-3,300 ha and the area of forest pastures (in Finnish: *metsälaitumia*) to about 5,000-9,000 ha. The quality of the remaining woody traditional biotopes has deteriorated considerably due to eutrophication and forestry operations. However, the maintenance of traditional biotopes, their landscape values and delivered ecosystem services provide opportunities for entrepreneurship and

development of modern silvopastoral systems. Government support is until now the main source of income for farms managing key biotopes and traditional rural landscapes by grazing. Nevertheless, there would be a range of opportunities to develop additional sources of side- or main income such as e.g., ecotourism, therapy and well-being services (Greencare), wild berry and mushroom cultivation, honey production, bioenergy production and direct sales of pasture meat.

Other types of agroforestry in Finland are scarce but there are good opportunities. Alley cropping is rarely practiced in Finland and the farmers practising it started relatively recently (2014-2022). As the Baltic Sea is surrounded by land, eutrophication is a major issue. Riparian buffer zones would improve water quality and would fit very well in the Finnish landscape.

2.7.2 FORMATION OF LIVING LAB FINLAND

The Finnish LL builds on the stakeholders who were active in the AFINET project (EURAF 2023a) and the Finnish Agroforestry Network. The Finnish Agroforestry Network was established in June 2019 at Qvidja farm at a joint workshop organised by the AFINET project, Baltic Sea Action Group, Natural Resources Institute Finland, several farmers and other people interested in agroforestry. The aim of the Finnish Agroforestry Network is to share knowledge on agroforestry between practitioners, advisors, researchers and policy. The network is active in organising field trips, lectures and monthly online meeting to bring the different stakeholders together and share information and update each other on activities related to agroforestry. The Finnish Agroforestry Network became EURAF member in June 2022 and this has helped a lot in activating the network.

Preparations for setting up the Finnish LL were done mainly by presenting the project at various events. It was presented twice during the monthly Finnish Agroforestry Network meetings and also during a public agroforestry seminar organised by the Tropical Resources Institute of the University of Helsinki in November 2022. In addition, people were invited to sign up for the Finnish LL by e-mail.

Figure 6. *Location of the Living Lab in southern (Uusimaa) and eastern Finland (North Karelia).*

2.7.3 COMPOSITION OF LIVING LAB FINLAND

The initial LL was formed in January 2023 when the first online meeting took place. A second meeting will take place in August 2023.

The LL focusses on two regions in Finland; the region of Uusimaa (Nyland) in southern Finland and the region of Pohjois-Karjala (North-Karelia) in eastern Finland (Figure 6). The two regions are very different as Nyland is the most populated region of the country and is mainly characterised by urban areas in Helsinki Metropolitan area and the surrounding farmland. North Karelia is sparsely populated and mainly covered by forests.

The two LL regions focus on different agroforestry systems. The LL in southern Finland will focus on arable agroforestry systems such as alley cropping. The LL in eastern Finland will focus on silvopastoral agroforestry systems such as forest grazing and wood pastures. Even though the focus of the LL is on these two regions, we warmly welcome participants from other regions in Finland to join the LL.

The LL now consists of a bit more than 10 individuals:

- Policy is represented by a person working at the Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry and an assistant of a Finnish member of the European Parliament.
- The practitioners are represented by six farmers from different agricultural sectors: four arable farmers and two livestock farmers. Farm advisors are represented by a person from ProAgria, the Finnish Farm Advisory extension service. ProAgria has large expertise on sheep farming and management of natural pastures, but expertise on alley cropping is lacking.
- The Value Chain is represented by a person working at Valio, which is the largest dairy producer in Finland. Valio is especially interested in ways to integrate agroforestry in their own Carbon Calculator and in developing Biodiversity Footprinting methods for their products.
- Several researchers from Natural Resources Institute Finland (LUKE) and Helsinki University have joined the LL. Some of them have experience with agroforestry in Finland while others would like to learn more. At Helsinki University they have a large expertise on agroforestry in the tropics but not much on the possibilities in Finland.
- Some teachers would also like to join. The teachers were represented by a person from LIVIA vocational school and three persons from NOVA University of Applied Sciences. Involving teachers would be highly beneficial for the aims of the project because they will train the advisors and farmers of the future. The teachers were mainly interested in information that can be used for developing their teaching materials, as well as digital tools and data that can be used in teaching as well as for use in practical training assignments.

It is expected that the composition of the group can still change during the project. Survey about usage and needs of digital tools in practice

3. Survey about usage and needs of digital tools in practice

3.1 Method

3.1.1 PREPARATION OF THE SURVEY

Objective

The main goal of this survey was to discover the perception of stakeholders involved in agroforestry (farmers, advisors, researchers, policy-makers, etc.) regarding aspects related to agroforestry practices in Europe (policy, biodiversity, agronomy, financial, use and needs of digital tools) and their use of, need and wants for (digital) tools and sharing knowledge.

The DigitAF joint survey was developed as structured and self-administered, although individual LLs could choose to administer the questionnaire through video calls or phone calls to optimize data collection and guide the intended user through the questions. Still, all questions should be administered following the same protocol and assuring the absence of bias or encouragement towards certain responses.

The goal was to develop a survey that would not be too long or complex, limiting the questions to those necessary to provide the data for analysis. Questions were formulated in a clear, non-biased way.

Survey development and structure

Each WP collected topics and questions, which were summarized into an initial survey setup. This was discussed in the broader working group of the DigitAF project, was modified and discussed in light of short-term and long-term objectives.

To gain knowledge regarding survey design in agriculture contexts, various sources were consulted, providing insights on case studies and survey development, administering and data analysis (Nguyen-Thi-Lan et al. 2021). This resulted in an itinerary survey design process, paired with input implementation from the survey working group, ultimately resulting in the survey presented in Annex I. The whole survey takes 1-1.5 h to complete, depending on the stakeholder type. The final survey structure can be found in Table 3.

Table 3. Structure of the DigitAF-Survey

Section	Subject	Stakeholder type	Estimated time to complete (min)
1	<i>General characteristics of respondents</i>	All	4
2	<i>Experience of digital tools in farming systems</i>	All	6
3	<i>Agroforestry and digital tools</i> Agroforestry knowledge and perception and digital tools in agroforestry systems	All	6
4	<i>Detailed questions on digital models and tools for agroforestry:</i> Policy-related questions Technical, economic and administrative issues Tree, crop and animal interactions questions Biodiversity-related questions	Farmers & policymakers All All All	5 8 10 6

5	<i>Social/ psychological aspects related to digital models and tools in agroforestry</i>	Farmers	13
6	<i>Conclusive part of the survey:</i> Communication	All	3
	Further interest to receive updates from the DigitAF project and agroforestry related activities	All	2

3.1.2 TECHNICAL ASPECTS, WORKFLOW AND SURVEY DISTRIBUTION

Coordination efforts by WP4 and UNIPI consisted of receiving input from different work packages (Figure 7), converting and adapting questions into Google Form, language and spelling revisions and merging, removing, adding questions and sections as well as implementing improvements and changes both discussed during meetings and received via emails.

Figure 1. Visual representation of contributions from different Work Packages.

The team put a great deal of importance on making the survey GDPR compliant. Therefore, a privacy notice was inserted at the beginning of the survey and it was also anonymized, disabling the Google form function allowing to record emails of users. Furthermore, codes were assigned to users from each LL leader, which was stored by each individual LL managers. The data originating from each LL, is safely and anonymously stored in each LL folder, with every Google form being able to automatically generate one or multiple google sheets containing responses.

The survey was translated into each of the LL languages, and (minimally) adapted to facilitate comprehension and make questions more relevant to the local context.

The choice was to first distribute the survey to LL participants, to collect 10-15 responses per LL and to end up with a total of 60- 90 responses over all LLs.

3.1.3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The outcomes were analysed per LL by LL managers. This report only reports the main outcomes of the survey and meetings to outline the most important needs and expectations of the stakeholders.

3.2 Outcomes

The needs and wants per Living Lab are discussed in the following subsections, starting with the three Advanced living labs, followed by the seed living labs.

3.2.1 THE NETHERLANDS

Respondents

The survey was filled out by 14 respondents, all active members of the LL The Netherlands. All respondents were between 18 and 65 years of age from different age groups and genders. Farmers and land owners (5) and policymakers (5) make up the largest group of respondents, followed by advisors (3). Only one value chain stakeholder filled in the survey. This is a representative reflection

of the LL as well as the Dutch agroforestry sector. All farmers within the LL have experience with agroforestry. More than half of the respondents indicate they have completed a university master's degree. The outcomes of the survey were presented to 12 of the LL members to discuss the outcomes in further depth.

Experience with digital tools

The survey shows limited use of digital tools across all stakeholders. Geographical data, data on soil characteristics, nutrients and policy-related data are mostly used via digital tools. Tools for data about energy, greenhouse gas emission and biodiversity were not much used. However, when discussing the results, members of the LL realised they use digital tools more often than they actually realized. Respondents are not always aware of the fact that they are using techniques that can be classified as digital tools. Tools for registration of land use and management are often mandatory. When designing agroforestry, map tools are regularly used to access geographical as well as policy data.

Agroforestry and digital tools

Members of the LL agreed upon a high demand for digital tools for the management of an agroforestry system. These include: tools for system design, tree selection, crop, tree and animal performance and management of agroforestry systems. Also, tools on economic aspects of agroforestry systems as well as tools on environmental aspects (biodiversity, carbon neutrality, soil health) are valued. Digital tools are expected to be of added value especially to overcome the complexity of these topics and to make data easier available. On the contrary, many of the LL members are slightly reluctant to the use of digital tools. This is partially caused by the workload of the already present digital administration tools, that in some cases creates reality of numbers on paper that doesn't reflect the actual reality.

Stakeholders have a critical attitude towards predictive models for agroforestry systems. It is expected that the complexity and locally deviating contexts, combined with a lack of local data, cause high levels of inaccuracy. At the same time, LL members are aware that predictive models are merely a reflection of reality and could nevertheless be useful as decision-making tools. The most preferred devices to use digital tools are PCs (laptop and desktop) (71%) and smartphones (57%). Tablets are not often used for digital tools (14%).

Needs and expectations on project-related themes

Policy – Farmers (80%) replied they are interested in carbon farming, but that this very much depends on the conditions and details, as they also explained in LL meetings. Policymakers indicated they are very interested in how their international colleagues are stimulating agroforestry in their respective countries. Policymakers were interested in a broad range of indicators. The respondents confirmed that the Dutch LPIS isn't perfectly suited to administrate agroforestry yet. Farmers experience it to be hard and time-consuming to administrate their agroforestry fields. And the LPIS doesn't give insights to policymakers about where agroforestry fields are, nor what area of agroforestry is currently present in the Netherlands.

Technical, economic and administrative issues – Most of the respondents indicated that technical knowledge, the complexity of AF systems as well as the level of knowledge regarding the management of trees on farmland was problematic. Valuable digital tools on these subjects should include tools to provide practical knowledge or provide decision support on crop and variety selection, management, and machinery. In the LL meeting, practitioners felt that a tool to predict and manage labour is most valuable.

Concerning the economic obstacles, the respondents indicated that the necessity of large investments to set up AF systems are very problematic. Other obstacles (costs of management, access to financing, diminished income) are also experienced as problematic. Digital tools should therefore aim at

recording or predicting the costs and benefits of agroforestry systems and predicting economic performance of different management strategies.

Concerning policy, digital tools could help to provide a better insight into all the legislation involved. Since a website is available for this (www.ruimtelijkeplannen.nl) the complexity is probably an inherent part of the policy itself.

Tree, crop and animal interactions – Most respondents replied that tools for AF system design would be useful. Respondents selected many parameters that should be included in such a design tool, such as soil condition, tree and crop choice, and tree management. Also, hydrology, mechanisation, water management, biodiversity and carbon sequestration optimisation, and topography were rated as important. In the LL meeting, it was emphasized a tool should also be able to compare the performance of an agroforestry system with a monoculture system. They didn't know a AF design tool already existed in the Dutch language (Agroforestry Planner, Flanders). This shows the importance of communication about existing agroforestry tools. A tool for selecting tree species and varieties was also mentioned as much needed.

The respondents also indicated that digital tools for predicting crop and tree performances would be useful. In the LL meeting, it was agreed that tree performance might be more important than crop predictions, signalling a lack of knowledge about the performance of trees by the farmers.

Furthermore, digital tools for tree management were mentioned as useful. Most important parameters for a tool for tree management include pruning requirements, tree health check and productivity optimization.

Digital tools for animal performance were mentioned as valuable. It is important to note that silvopastoral agroforestry in The Netherlands is by far the most common form of agroforestry in The Netherlands. When selecting important parameters to include in such a tree management tool, respondents ranked the aspects (tree) fodder provision, animal health, and risk of intoxication as most important, followed by most of the other predefined options.

During open discussion, it was mentioned that a tool for visualisation of AFS would be helpful, both on field scale and on landscape scale. Also, a tool to promote agroforestry was suggested and agreed upon by other LL members. Furthermore, it was suggested to build a tool to record (register) the current agroforestry system (labour activities, yields, costs and observations) for the farmers to get an overview on these subjects and to collect vast amounts of data in different contexts. This also creates possibilities to develop a tool for sharing best practices, which is another strong need expressed by practitioners.

Respondents indicated that existing tools on other subjects than agroforestry often lack user-friendliness expressed by a lack of intuitive use, attractive layout, flexibility (to change inputs and to adapt to local conditions) and reliability (of information and performance). Furthermore, it is important the tool can be accessed in the field.

Biodiversity – The majority (90%) of the respondents indicated that biodiversity in agroecosystems is very important. However, not many knew tools for assessing biodiversity of agroforestry systems, and the respondents doubted whether a digital tool would be helpful for this. In a discussion during the LL meeting, it became clear that increasing biodiversity is a vital motive to start with agroforestry, but due to the complexity of biodiversity, other ecosystem services were presumed to be easier monitored and valued. Tools assessing biodiversity in agroforestry systems are however extremely welcome.

3.2.2 GERMANY

Respondents

By the time of drafting the report, a total number of twelve persons have responded to the online questionnaire, from which ten are associated with the Living Lab in Germany. With respect to the age classification, over 80% of the respondents formed a bi-modal distribution from the younger age group 18-35 years and the older age group 51 to 65 years. Three quarter reported their gender as male, one quarter as female. The most prominent group of participants were farmers, followed by representatives from politics & administration. The respondent's background thus reflects the predominantly approached target groups. Representatives from education and research sciences were the third most prominent group.

Experience with digital tools

Eleven of the respondents use a number of digital tools. The majority use digital tools for the support of upcoming decisions. Not so common seems the use of digital tools for the performance of exercises or for the purpose of work organisation or documentation. 18% of the respondent do not use digital tools.

The most useful digital models or tools mentioned by four respondents were MS Excel, FarmOS, Landscape Architect/CAD, drawing programs, Geodata from the state, GIS and Weather forecasts. When it comes to the quality and abilities of digital tools, comments refer to A) the user experience and B) the actual tasks/capabilities, in summary:

- A) The tools should be designed to be easy and intuitive to use in order to save time for the users, practical and require a low technical and learning effort. Tools should have a good graphical user interface and provide a pleasant user experience, are self-explanatory with helpful error messages and fast support to users. They can be used on mobile phones and even with interrupted input or without an internet connection as well as decentralized.
- B) Tools should provide real decision-making support, allowing for easy input and editing of data, as well as an exchange of data and access to data from all entities involved. Thus, the tools' compatibility with other applications seems important. They should be adapted to fit the user's own business processes, provide reliable results and recommendations, understandable and practical. The tools designed should be specifically applicable to solve a particular problem.

Agroforestry and digital tools

The knowledge about agroforestry normally distributed, with the majority on knowledge Level 3 (Figure 8). However, slightly skewed towards Level 4.

Figure 2. "How would you rate your knowledge of agroforestry systems?" (Scale: 1 "low level" to 5 "high level")

Needs and expectations on project-related themes

Policy – Six respondents considered themselves a farmer and were willing to answer the questions about politics. From that group, two third showed interest already in the support programs of the CAP in the field of agroforestry within the framework of the previous CAP period 2014-2022. The vast majority (83.3%) are currently interested in funding programmes from the CAP.

Technical, economic and administrative issues – With respect to future utilisation in the use and development of digital tools, the LPIS is of utter importance. These data are of high confidentiality in Germany. The use and application is usually denied by the administrations, as the system was set up to be of administrative concern of the IACS only.

Surprisingly, 50% of the farmers agreed to the use of LPIS data within the project, and a third would potentially agree, after a detailed discussion. No one denied data access. When being asked to list and rank any other technical or agronomic barriers to the use of agroforestry in Germany, see Table 4.

Table 4. *Other technical or agronomic barriers to the use of agroforestry in Germany*

Level	Answers
Somewhat problematic (Level 2):	“Availability of small tractors” “Availability of machines for harvesting and tending”
Very problematic (Level 3):	“Little integration in studies” “Availability of technical resources for the management of AFS for energetic use” “Lack of political support for implementation”
Extremely problematic (Level 4):	“Ignorance of administration (authorities)” “Little integration in professional training (gardeners, farmers)”

3.2.3 ITALY

Respondents

At present, the full LL survey has recorded 12 responses. Respondents were mostly aged 18-35 or 36-50 and a 58-42 male–female ratio. Most of the respondents are agricultural consultants (42%), followed by farmers and landowners (25%). The practice is therefore well represented. 60% of respondents also have a secondary stakeholder role

Experience with digital tools

Respondents use digital tools mostly for Decision support and research purposes, as well as for educational purposes. Users stated they use or used in the past a vast range of data: climate and weather data, geographical data, policy-related data etc. Models are used mostly for technical and economic subjects.

Agroforestry and digital tools

Users indicated that a management-related tool for agroforestry could be particularly useful for setting up agroforestry systems, determining crop and livestock performance or selecting tree species. They indicated that a tool related to agroforestry-related CAP matters could be of great relevance. From an environmental point of view, users would appreciate a tool or model aiding them in evaluating the carbon neutrality of agroforestry systems.

Needs and expectations on project-related themes

The following sections present a summary of the obstacles and needs that users indicated during the first LL meeting, presented in the relevant categories (policy, technical and economic)

Policy aspects

- Cultural and skills challenges in implementing policies effectively.
- Management difficulties and inadequate economic support.
- Difficulty in classifying systems and providing clear guidelines.
- Lack of incentives and rewards for farmers adopting agroforestry practices.
- Limited availability of quality propagation material at affordable prices.
- Complex and non-streamlined rules hindering the development of woodland grazing.
- Long-term planning requirements for effective policy implementation.
- Lack of forward-looking nature conservation policies at the territorial level.
- Non-economic recognition of ecosystem value and agroforestry-pastoral traditions.
- Resistance, high initial costs, and lack of economic incentives for primary operators.
- Disconnect between the political and agricultural worlds.
- Territorial differences, incompatible tools, low valorisation, and coexistence challenges.
- Lack of cultural awareness and perception of profitability in agroforestry.
- Superficial and opportunistic policy interest without sustained commitment.

Technical, economic and administrative issues

- Requirement of large surfaces and suitable equipment: agroforestry systems often require extensive land areas and specific equipment, which can pose challenges for implementation.
- Difficulties in system management and lack of comprehensive knowledge: Both technicians and farmers may face difficulties in managing the complex components of agroforestry systems due to a lack of adequate knowledge.
- Compatibility of tree rows with mechanization and farmer unfamiliarity: Farmers may struggle with managing tree rows that are compatible with mechanized operations, and they may lack experience in tasks such as tree care and pruning. Additionally, there may be challenges in properly declaring agroforestry arable land in the company records.
- Economic issue: Limited consumer knowledge and ageing demographics: Consumers may have limited understanding of agroforestry products, and the presence of elderly buyers with less technical knowledge can further hinder adoption. Rural areas experiencing depopulation and reduced services exacerbate these challenges.
- Lack of academic knowledge transfer and limited interest from the scientific community: Adequate knowledge and information exchange between academia and practitioners is often lacking, with limited interest and attention from the scientific community.
- Small land parcels and company distrust: The presence of small land parcels and a general lack of trust in the system can impede adoption and implementation. Concerns about management skills, costs, and identifying economically sustainable solutions also contribute to this obstacle.
- Need for shared interventions and medium to long-term planning: Successful implementation of agroforestry systems requires collaboration, shared decision-making, and long-term planning. Finding economically viable solutions that benefit all stakeholders is crucial.
- Lack of knowledge and perceived profitability: Limited understanding and trust in the potential profitability of agroforestry can discourage farmers from engaging in such practices.
- Unique nature of each company/territory: The diversity and uniqueness of each company and territory make it challenging to develop generalized models that can be applied on a large

scale. Additionally, the inclusion of agricultural variables in data analysis poses further difficulties.

Economic aspects

- Initial investments and reshaping of company management: Small and medium enterprises face challenges in making the necessary initial investments and adjusting their management practices to adopt agroforestry systems.
- Higher production costs and market availability: Agroforestry products may be less competitive in the market due to higher production costs compared to conventional systems, potentially resulting in limited availability of these products.
- Need for economic support and market uncertainty: Economic support is required for the initial investment and management of agroforestry plants, and there is uncertainty regarding market demand and which tree species will generate income in the long term.
- General ignorance and agricultural crisis: There is a lack of awareness and understanding of agroforestry practices, compounded by the ongoing economic crisis in the agricultural sector.
- Costs charged to the product and lack of recognition: The costs associated with managing agroforestry systems are often borne by the product, without proper recognition from the production system.
- Unprofitability and lack of initial investment: Agroforestry systems may face challenges in achieving profitability, which can discourage initial investment.
- Difficulty accessing incentives and lack of certification systems: Difficulty in accessing incentive measures, along with a lack of recognition for environmental performance, and the absence of widely recognized certification systems pose obstacles.
- Lack of guarantor/system certification and consumer information: The absence of a reliable guarantor or certification system, along with limited consumer information and awareness about agroforestry, hinders market acceptance.
- Market risks and perception of deception: There is a risk that the current focus on short-term sustainability concerns could undermine the market potential for agroforestry products if consumers perceive them as deceptive or lacking long-term viability.

3.2.4 CZECHIA

Respondents

During the second meeting of the LL Czechia, the extensive survey (translated to Czech language) was explained to all the participants and following the meeting, all received the online link to fill out the survey. Up to now, 20 participants (50%) of the LL Czechia answered the survey (3 policymakers, 11 practitioners and 6 beneficiaries). The reminder was sent to the remaining participants and we expect to finally reach at least 75% response rate of all LL participants.

Experience with digital tools

In total ¾ of the respondents currently use digital tools for their decision-making, most often geo/mapping tools, weather forecast tools, legislation, and soil/nutrient/fertilization tools. Specifically, the respondents often mention freely available tools and software like LPIS, cadastre maps, weather forecast, etc. But at this moment they do not use any specific tool for agroforestry. They also stressed that the tools must be user friendly, simple and with a good visualisation for them to be used.

Agroforestry and digital tools

More than half of the respondents evaluate themselves to possess relatively good knowledge about agroforestry, and more than 90% of farmers want to establish agroforestry in the future. More than

80% of farmers also think about carbon farming. The greatest need for agroforestry would be a suitable tool for tree selection, design, and management. A very useful tool would also be a financial evaluation of AF, and soil health management. The respondents also put a very strong emphasis on the importance of biodiversity and any tool for its evaluation. The best tool should be used on smartphone or laptop/PC.

Needs and expectations on project-related themes

Policy - Nearly all practitioners (farmers and advisors) are interested in the possible support of agroforestry and carbon farming in the current CAP. Most of them are interested in the results from EU monitoring of erosion. Nearly all farmers have identified tree landscape features (hedges, isolated trees, lines of trees, groups of trees) on their farm, they want to establish new ones, and a large proportion also have forest plots on their land.

Technical, economic and administrative issues - The farmers are aware of the complexity of AF, some of them feel obstacles in the available knowledge about planting trees on agricultural land, suitable tree species and tree seedlings. However, the most problematic aspects seem to be the high investment costs for AF establishment and management, and especially administrative burden connected with growing trees on agricultural land.

Tree, crop and animal interactions - The farmers do not feel the tree, crop and animal production as very problematic issue and claim they are able to manage it.

Biodiversity - The participants claim the maintenance and improvement of biodiversity on agricultural land as a very important issue. They are available to invest their time for the monitoring of biodiversity and would like to use a specific digital tool to do this. Most of them are not aware of any of them.

3.2.5 FINLAND

Respondents

The first Living Lab workshop took place online on the 10th of January 2023 and was attended by 10 persons (4 farmers, 2 researchers, 2 teachers, and 2 advisors). The workshop started with a short introduction and overview of the aims and planned activities in the DigitAF project. In the second part of the workshop, there were discussions on the current use of digital tools and brainstorming sessions (using the Mural Canvass tool) on what kind of tools and on which topic digital tools would be useful.

The survey was launched on the 25th of May and a reminder was sent on the 9th of June. So far there are only three answers (1 farmer, 1 researcher/farmer, 1 researcher). To gather more responses, we will approach some of the LL members directly and ask them if they would like to complete the survey.

Experience with digital tools

During the workshop, the participants mentioned that they do not use any digital tools in managing their farms. However, very soon it turned out that actually each of them uses digital tools and some of them are highly adapted in using digital tools, even some very advanced tools and models. Tools mentioned during the discussion were: the Contour map creator, ArcGIS, fertilizer calculator, education platforms (Moodle), spatial datasets, and the RUSLE soil erosion model.

From the online survey, it was emphasized that especially tools and datasets from the Finnish Geological Survey, the Finnish Environment Centre (SYKE), Natural Resources Institute Finland (LUKE), and Open Forest Data provided by the Finnish Forest Centre (Metsäkeskus), are particularly useful and are of good quality. It was also noted that tools must be user friendly, easy to use and with good visualisation functionality.

Agroforestry and digital tools

Two third of the survey participants considered themselves to have good to very good knowledge of agroforestry. Most useful (question 3.3) for implementing agroforestry would be tools for tree selection in AF, planning of AF systems, tree yield, crop yield, animal production, and management and governance decision support systems in agroforestry. As an outcome of the workshop, tools would be useful on the following topics:

- Tools for carbon sequestration
- Tools for soil health
- Tools for biodiversity
- Tools for erosion control
- Tools for water management
- Economic planning, tools for profitability, economic sustainability
- Tools for adaptive management
- Visualisation tools, how do tree canopies develop and how to manage them?
- Decision support systems for initial planning of new agroforestry areas
- Tools and models what can be used in teaching agronomy students or for use in practical training and assignments

Needs and expectations on project related themes

Policy – 100% (n=2) of the respondents were interested in possible support for agroforestry and carbon farming in the new CAP for 2023-2028. 50% of the respondents are planning to introduce new tree landscape features and 50% of the respondents are planning to implement new agroforestry areas. 100% of the respondents is not satisfied with how tree landscape features are currently reported.

Technical, economic and administrative issues – The farmers see the higher complexity of AF as an obstacle for implementation, as well as the lack of knowledge, and the high investment costs for their establishment and management. Suitable tree species selection seems to be less problematic. In addition, the lack of advice, availability of tree seedlings, and the availability of demonstration sites and research on AF in Finland is seen as a serious barrier for uptake.

Tree, crop and animal interactions – All of the respondents are interested in tools for planning and evaluating different tree, crop and animal combinations. The tools can be used to see the impact of different tree/crop/animal combinations and compare it to the farmers' own plans. The tools can also be used to compare other possible combinations that the farmer might not have thought of him/herself. No one was aware of any tools which currently could be used for this purpose.

Tools were seen as useful because crop and livestock farmers probably don't have much knowledge of growing trees.

Biodiversity – All respondents found biodiversity in agricultural ecosystems extremely important and all of them saw the development of a possible model or tool very useful. Not any of the respondents was aware of the existence of a biodiversity tool. A tool could be useful for monitoring and improving the ecological state of agricultural land, it could encourage policymakers to make more funds available for safeguarding and enhancement of biodiversity, and a good ecological status of the land could even increase crop yields.

3.2.6 UNITED KINGDOM

The needs of UK agroforestry in general, and the Living Lab participants in particular, were discussed during the initial meeting of the UK Living Lab. The following issues were identified:

- Participants are eager to have new tools
- Participants are keen to receive updates on project progress
- There is a need for tools to design agroforestry systems
- Also, there is a need for tools to monitor changes in carbon accounting, ecosystem services (soil health, biodiversity, water quality), and micro-climate associated issues
- Another need is the need for tools to predict the economic impact of agroforestry systems
- A UK map of recent and current agroforestry research activity, in order to identify synergies and prevent duplication is desired
- There are potential links/integration of new agroforestry tools with existing tools and apps
- There is a need to make a choice of farming level within tools: field – farm – landscape
- In order to upscale agroforestry, there is a need to develop a market for agroforestry products and built a related infrastructure for that market

Respondents

The survey was filled by eight respondents. The reported ages of the respondents were five over 50 years old, two between 36-50 years old, and one between 18-35 years. Most of the respondents were men (5), with three women. Respondents were primarily using digital tools for research purposes (62.5%), but also for decision support (50%), and for training (37.5%).

Experience with digital tools

Geographical data is the most used type of data, followed by biodiversity, tree/crop species selection and soil and nutrients data. After that, energy and greenhouse gas data, and policy data, followed by climate and weather and economy data. Animal nutrition and welfare was the least used type of data. Respondents mentioned a handful of existing tools as useful.

Answers to 'What makes a good digital tool?' indicated that tools should be intuitive and user friendly, with good graphics, good guidance and clear instructions (technical and practical guides supported by evidence), but flexible and compatible with other products. Accessibility, modularity, accuracy, whole-farm approach, ability to add layers of maps, useful outputs, relevant, and thorough were also mentioned.

Agroforestry and digital tools

Most of the respondents had a relatively high knowledge of agroforestry and a fair idea of specific agroforestry practices. All the proposed tools for the management, economic aspects and environmental aspects of agroforestry systems were regarded as very useful or useful. When asked about preferred platform for the tools, laptops and desktops ranked highest (87.5%), closely followed by smartphones (75%), then tablets (37.5%).

Needs and expectations on project-related themes

Policy: Of all respondents 25% were farmers, 37.5% policymakers, 37.5% were nor farmers nor policymakers. One of the most striking results is that no one have heard of the Farm Suitability Tool (FaST) System.

Technical, economic and administrative issues- Respondents perceived the following as most problematic obstacles to the application of agroforestry:

- Technical obstacles: increased complexity in agroforestry systems, level of knowledge regarding tree management, interaction with livestock, knowledge network on technical issues, and

technical knowledge of workers, availability of management resources, fruit/nut harvesting, and water provision of young trees. Other technical obstacles: identifying routes to market and availability of tree material for agroforestry systems.

- Economic obstacles: access to financing, necessity of initial large investment, management costs, diminished income of primary crops, insufficient future revenue. Other economic obstacles mentioned were quality of planting stock and lack of UK-based data on cost/benefit analysis of different agroforestry systems.
- Administration obstacles: land ownership issues, issues with permits for planting/removing trees.

Tree, soil and animal interactions – A new tool for the design as well as for tree species/variety selection of agroforestry systems is thought as useful as 75% of respondents were not aware of existing tools, with user friendliness and visualisation being the aspects with more room for improvement. All the suggested parameters to be included were regarded as relevant.

A new tool for crop and tree performance , for tree management and for animal performance in agroforestry is regarded as useful as 50% (for crop and tree performance) and 87.5% (for tree management and animal performance) of respondents were not aware of existing tools, with user friendliness, visualisation and scale being the aspects with more room for improvement. All the suggested parameters to be included were regarded as relevant.

Other support needs: ecosystem services valuation.

Biodiversity related questions

Biodiversity is considered an important subject in agroforestry and most respondents (87.5%) are not aware of existing tools. A web-based (75%) or freely available computer programme tool would be preferable for respondents. Farm level is the most popular spatial scale for the tool. Most respondents think that the tool should be constructed using a mixed approach, combining a checklist of the current management and status of farm/field and whole farm audits. Most of the suggested species' groups were considered relevant.

4 Conclusion and outlook

4.2 Conclusion

Despite the different contexts all the members of the Living Labs operate in, a large part of the needs and wants overlap. For example, the actors have a positive attitude towards the development of a (European) map of agroforestry practitioners and other actors. Also in most LL, the centre of gravity of needs and wants are tools for agroforestry practitioners and advisors. There is a high demand for tools for the design and management of agroforestry systems, as well as decision support tools on the topic of financial aspects and tree and crop performance. The prediction as well as the monitoring of ecosystem services (with emphasis on carbon sequestration and biodiversity) is also an important topic for tool development. For practitioners, this topic is important in order to make well-informed choices in their farm management, for policymakers to track progress on certain indicators and for beneficiaries in the value chain to properly substantiate that agroforestry products are products with added value for society. Furthermore, all LL made suggestions to increase user-friendliness by making tools available on mobile phones in the field, taking into account that tools must be accessed quick and easy, often without an internet connection.

In the previous chapters the use, wants and needs of the six Living Labs were explained and discussed on the basis of LL meetings and survey outcomes. Hereafter, the most important outcomes per LL are presented with their relation to different work packages of the DigitAF project.

The Netherlands (advanced)

Most important outcomes	Related WP				
	1	2	3	4	5
Need for a tool for quantitative / positive communication about Agroforestry	x		x		x
Need for AF Map – to connect and (re)present AF, include other stakeholders	x		x		x
Need for tree decision tool, what tree in what context		x			
Need for tree performance tool (yield, growth, labour prediction)		x			
Need for a tool to record and predict/plan management (labour)		x			
Tools should be user friendly: flexible, reliable, intuitive	x	x	x	x	x
Be clear about what data is used in the tool (source/context), it is expected there is a lack of data specific to Dutch conditions to make a proper tool	x	x	x	x	x

Germany (advanced)

Most important outcomes	Related WP				
	1	2	3	4	5
Tools should be: easy, intuitive, time saving, practical, low technical and learning barriers, good GUI, pleasant UX, useable on a smartphone, offline, easy input of data	x	x	x	x	
Most interesting seem tools for design of agroforestry systems and the choice of trees, on the contrary, growth models and management seem to be of low/ no interest, especially as they have doubts in the predictability of tree performance and the necessity of a software to assist with tree care		x			
E.g. specific cultivar selection, 71% for high, and 28% for very high, especially the optimal site-adapted selection of trees is of high interest, no one has experience in this field of tools yet		x			

Tools for economic efficiency can be very useful, the identification of suppliers and financing options incl. subsidies are seen less useful.		x	x		
The usefulness of environmental performance tools is seen somewhat critical and seen with a “certain interest”, but rarely of “very high interest”, with the exception of carbon storage		x	x		
The current map of agroforestry in Germany is not known well enough but those who know it, see the benefits			x		X

Italy (advanced)

Most important outcomes	Related WP				
	1	2	3	4	5
High interest in digital tools but we need Italian data collection to validate tools		x		x	
Limits for agroforestry transition due to policy development	x				x
Request for a sustainability assessment tool but the question is how to standardise data collection			x	x	
Tool for agroforestry design		x			
Tool for carbon removal assessment	x		x		
Predictive tool for system performance (tree-crop-animal) and entire value chain		x	x	x	

Czechia (seed)

Most important outcomes	Related WP				
	1	2	3	4	5
Use of digital tools by groups of beneficiaries	x	x	x		
Tools should be user friendly: flexible, reliable, intuitive	x	x	x		
Need for tree decision tool, what tree in what context		x			
Need for tools for design and management of AFS		x			
Need for tool for financial performance of AFS		x	x		
Need for tool for biodiversity performance of AFS			x		
Need for tool for soil health performance of AFS			x		

Finland (seed)

Most important outcomes	Related WP				
	1	2	3	4	5
Tools must be user friendly, easy to use and with good visualization functions	x	x	x	x	x
Need for tools for tree selection in AF (which tree species, visualisation tools, how do tree canopies develop and how to manage them, tree yield tools)		x			
Need for tools for planning of AF systems (how to get started, planning new AF systems)		x			
Need for tools for carbon sequestration	x		x		
Need for tools for soil health			x		
Need for tools for biodiversity			x		
Need for tools for erosion control		x			
Need for tools for water management		x			
Need for tools for economic planning, profitability and economic sustainability		x	x		

United Kingdom (seed)

Most important outcomes	Related WP				
	1	2	3	4	5
Need for AF system design tools to estimate and monitor changes in carbon accounting, ecosystem services, microclimate and economic impacts	x	x	x		
Need for AF national research map, recent and current activities	x		x	x	x
Need for linkage/integration of new tools with existing tools	x	x	x	x	
The level on which the tool is made (field / farm / landscape) is crucial	x	x	x		
Upscaling: need for development of market and related infrastructure			x		x

Despite the many similarities between LL, the specific context of the different LL ensures that the wishes with regard to tools also differ from each other. To be able to meet these wishes as much as possible, tailor-made solutions must be found.

4.3 Outlook

To secure efficient information transfer between the LLs and the work packages the following steps are proposed:

Complete the match-making exercise between identified needs and available tools and data

As part of the DigitAF project, an inventory is made of existing tools and data sources. The next step is to explore which (parts of) existing tools and datasets match the needs and wants of the LL members and selected the most promising. A crucial step in this process is to prioritise the needs and wants of the Living Labs.

Assess the appropriateness of selected tools in collaboration with LL participants

The most promising tools should be demonstrated to the LL. The LL can also report on needs and wants that are completely unmet and therefore new tools need to be developed.

Iterative testing and further development of tools

An iterative process is proposed in which the LL members are testing existing tools and provide their feedback to suggest adjustments and tweaks of the tool to the DigitAF consortium. The need to maintain cohesiveness and avoid fragmentation between tools (WPs) was highlighted.

Collect needs and wants from more actors

It is suggested to shorten the survey and send it out to a larger group of relevant actors outside of the LL. By reaching out to more actors in a greater number of European countries information can be collected to ensure the agroforestry tools are used by a wider audience.

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